

Exploring the Digital Life of Urban Parks Through Mobile Traffic

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Abstract—Experts look at urban parks in terms of form and function, usually focusing on park forms and with limitations in exploring function. These studies quantify the spatial and temporal presence of people in parks using small-scale surveys and movement data (e.g., GPS, check-ins), or general usage data (e.g., Call Detail Records (CDR)), but neglected analyzing activities and motivations for visiting parks, limiting the current understanding of the functional roles parks have in a city. On this work, we’ll go over how it’s possible to leverage measurements from mobile networks to explore the diversity of urban parks and explore how people may utilize them differently, according to the patterns of application-level traffic. We explore data obtained from large-scale measurements in Paris to reveal how the consumption of mobile applications can reveal different functional usages of urban parks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding how parks are used is crucial so urban planners can optimize the design and management of these areas. This is usually achieved by considering their form (e.g., the amount and type of greenery) and functions (e.g., do they promote specific sport activities, socializing, or nature-appreciations). With the widespread use of smartphones, mobile application traffic patterns, which act as a promising proxy for the presence and movement of populations in specific areas, have already proven useful in revealing detailed and nuanced usage patterns across different urban areas, offering a promising approach for understanding the patterns and types of urban park usage across different times and contexts.

Previous studies that explored urban green space utilization through mobile phone data either focused on datasets that showcase movement without mobile traffic usage—such as GPS [1], [2] and traffic signaling [3]—examined usage patterns without context, like CDR data [4], or analyzed traffic from a single application such as Strava [5]. Consequently, while these provided insights into park access, they did not delve into the specifics of mobile app usage within parks, leaving gaps in understanding beyond just the timing of visits. For this work, we leverage a large-scale app-level mobile traffic dataset (collected from Jan. 31 to May 31, 2023), selecting urban parks in Paris we’re able to distinguish traffic consumed inside from outside of parks. Our results showcase how people not only interact with their smartphones differently in these spaces, but also how different types of parks lead to different smartphone behaviors.

II. RESULTS

People use different apps in parks compared to the city. With a final set of 45 parks located in Paris and its suburbs that we’re confident that we can isolate its traffic from the neighborhood, we explore and characterize how these parks influence smartphone utilization versus the rest of the city, as well as if there’s uniformity of smartphone usage across parks. To compare mobile app usage within parks to that in other urban spaces, we select 41 relevant mobile apps, which together account for 80% of the non-encrypted traffic, and organize them into nine categories. Fig. 1A shows the application preference (represented by the Relative Symmetric Comparative Advantage (RSCA) metric) for these app categories in both parks and city areas, with * representing categories that have a statistical difference between the distribution of app usage between parks and the city (obtained from a t-test across distributions).

Park-specific applications: Apps in the music and news categories stand out as being used significantly more in parks compared to other areas of the city. This difference in mean usage is statistically significant, as confirmed by a *t*-test (*p*-value < 0.005 for music, and 0.049 for news). While categories such as fitness, video, shopping, and travel also tend to be more prevalent in parks on average, their differences with the rest of the city are less pronounced and do not reach statistical significance.

City-specific applications: On the other hand, app categories like social media and games are used significantly more in the rest of the city compared to parks, as indicated by a notable difference in the mean of the distributions (*p*-values of 0.005 and 0.027, respectively). Social media apps have negative RSCA values in parks, while most of the city shows positive values, indicating under-utilization in parks. Gaming apps are also under-utilized in parks, but are used more evenly across the city.

Despite the differences across apps, the confidence intervals (represented by lines) for RSCA values in parks show fluctuations between under- and over-utilization across some app categories (e.g., games). This variability suggests that app usage in parks is not uniform, indicating that we should next to explore patterns across parks.

Most parks see higher weekday use. To explore temporal

Fig. 1: (A) App preference between parks and city; (B) Weekday-to-weekend traffic ratio; (C) Park clusters across Paris; (D) Median week traffic and (E) App preference across clusters;

aspects of parks, we divide the total traffic volumes into weekdays and weekends. We found that approximately 75% of parks experience higher traffic on weekdays than on weekends (Fig. 1B). The variation in the traffic ratio, ranging from 0.72 to 1.86, is quite significant. The three parks with the *highest weekend traffic* are primarily oriented towards nature activities: Parc de la Fosse Maussain, Parc de la Vallée-aux-Loups and Parc Georges Brassens, and Parc de la Vallée-aux-Loups. The first two are located in the Parisian suburbs, feature dense green spaces. Meanwhile, the last is located more centrally, offers a pond, meadows, tree groves, and various gardens, including a vineyard. All are situated mostly in residential areas.

Conversely, from the three parks with the *highest weekday traffic*, Jardins Abbé Pierre and Parc Monceau are more central (with many business and universities nearby), while Parc Suzanne Lenglen is located on the southern outskirts of Paris (before the Suburbs). The latter park is a multi-sport facility park, used for sports classes, close to the Ministry of Defense and the digital business district in Issy-les-Moulineaux — which may explain its higher weekday usage.

Uncovering three functional uses of parks. We used each park’s per-application RSCA and weekday-to-weekend traffic ratio as features of a spectral cluster algorithm, finding 3 significant clusters through the Silhouette score. Besides an apparent spatial distribution across clusters (Fig. 1C), we note that the parks in each cluster show a variability in temporal traffic patterns (Fig. 1D) and differences in app preferences (Fig. 1E). Based on these patterns, we name clusters based on their functional uses: recreational, lunchbreak and cultural.

Recreational Parks (in blue) are located in the suburban areas of metropolitan Paris. According to the 2017 Census, 68% of the inhabitants of metropolitan Paris live in these less densely populated, mostly residential areas. Notably, parks in this category have the *lowest traffic consumption* compared to the those in the other two categories, using on average 55% less traffic.

Lunchbreak Parks (in green) are located in densely built areas near offices and universities. Their temporal traffic patterns are highly concentrated within work days, with the *median*

traffic being 58% higher on a workday compared to the weekend (these are mostly to the right of Fig. 1B). These are comparatively smaller, with their area being only 36% of the median area of the set. Their traffic patterns, proximity to business areas, and the types of apps used on workdays suggest that office workers frequent these parks during their work breaks.

Cultural Parks (in red) are mainly known for attractions such as the Champ de Mars with the Eiffel Tower, Jardin des Tuileries and Parc de la Vilette. Interestingly, those parks have an *even distribution of traffic across days*, with working days having only 7% more traffic than weekends. This could be explained by those parks being *popular throughout the week*, relating to the regions they are in and their tourist purpose in Paris.

How apps are used differently across park types. To understand how mobile app are used in each cluster, we calculate the application preference in each (Fig. 1E). *Cultural parks* experience a steady flow of visitors throughout the week, given their central locations and their role as cultural hubs. Social media and music streaming apps stood out with higher-than-average usage, likely driven by tourists who prioritize social engagement over apps related to shopping, games, productivity, or news while exploring the city. *Lunchbreak parks* follows a similar pattern, with social and music apps having a higher preference. This highlights how these two park types in the city center exhibit similar app usage patterns to the rest of the city (marked in black in Fig. 1E), indicating app consumption may not be influence by these parks. *Recreational parks* in contrast have distinct app usage patterns from all. Unlike cultural and lunchbreak parks, recreational parks exhibited higher usage across most app categories, except for music and social media. Notably, they were the only parks with increased usage in the fitness category, alongside higher engagement with news and travel apps.

These findings suggest that these spaces serve a unique role by offering settings for relaxation and everyday activities while promoting physical activity and reducing social media usage. When visitors used their phones, they tended to favor apps for reading and planning instead of social and music apps.

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